

PRESERVING THE EFFICACY OF ANTIMICROBIALS: AN IN-DEPTH EXPLORATION OF ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE

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ABSTRACT

Antimicrobial resistance is the global health issues that threatens the world, it is mainly prevalent in the European part of world. The antimicrobial resistance proves itself as a big challenge to the health officials and public health administrators, as the mutant strain are more resistant to that antibiotic. The antimicrobial resistance is not a singly controlled process, it not depends only on the genetic constitution of the microbes or their defense mechanism against the antibiotics, but the environmental effects, use of biocides, chemicals and heavy and radioactive elements increases the resistance against anti biotics. The antimicrobial resistance becoming an infectious disease in India and it

increasing at an exponential rate in other countries too. The current pandemic situation of corona virus is also an art of resistance, the virus mutates its genome and proves itself as a major challenge. No doubt that to combat the microbe's antibiotics as major weapon and these antimicrobials are used since decades as after the discovery of penicillin by Alexander Fleming but now days these antimicrobials are not used only for therapeutic purpose but also prophylactically in almost all industries like agriculture industries, animal husbandry and in food industries. After all these there occur uncertainty and the microbes becomes resistant to particular antibiotic and the patient or host is unaware that antibiotic resistance has developed. There are numerous infections like pneumonia, tuberculosis and gonorrhea that increases at alarming rate because many antibiotics are less effective. The development of anti-microbial resistance is somewhat directly proportional with the level of antibiotic consumption. The antibiotic treatment in the case of multiple drug resistant bacteria and multiple infection is getting harder day by day and their action spectrum is decreasing in exponential manner. The reason behind this is retailing the antibiotics in an unethical manner not following the proper guidelines and disposing the antibiotics over the counter. This increases the decrease in health

index rate against the multidrug resistant infections. In India there is alarming level of antimicrobial resistance development against pathogens like pseudomonas aeruginosa, salmonella, mycobacterium tuberculosis, Acinetobacter, shigella, klebsiella plasmodium, and HIV infection. Antimicrobial resistance is a multi-factorial problem and it hampers the existing health management system. In India around 7% of GDP spent on health management and monitoring system, and it is tremendously degraded by these resistant forms of infections. Poorly trained doctors practicing in unethical manner are also the cause of antimicrobial resistance. As there is very poor accountability for the use of antibiotics and it leads to many up short, the patient remain in disease state for longer time period and patient requires longer treatment against the disease, it might be expensive and may lead to toxicity that results in morbidity and mortality. The antimicrobial resistance hampers the success rate of treatments like organ transplantation, chemotherapy and other surgeries. The antimicrobial resistance pathway, starting from the gene level to the environmental level is a circularized process which completely effects the humans, animas, and the environment. The most common example of antimicrobial resistance affecting the environment is common mold called, Aspergillus fumigatus, found in the crop field in U.S. and it weakens the immune system. The resistant spores of microorganisms can transfer from the human to animals for example Salmonella Heidelberg that affects both human and animals.

KEYWORDS: Antimicrobial resistance, Antibiotics, microorganisms.

INTRODUCTION

Antimicrobial are the drugs which is used against the microbes, either inhibits their growth or kills them that is static or cidal.^[1-7] Antimicrobials are highly efficient against the bacteria and not respond to viral infections, these are use since very long time, and frequently use of these results into its resistance and also impart unwanted side effect.^[8] More the use of antibiotics more will be the resistance, almost are the microorganisms are resistant with the antibiotics. The antimicrobial resistance is more prevalent in children and older patient due to weak and undevelopment of immune system.

Antimicrobial drugs also regarded as antimicrobial, first antibiotic was discovered in 1928, penicillin by Alexander Fleming. Antibiotics are isolated from the natural sources and act against the life so called anti biosis that is against the life, they are derived from different spores of fungus or from other microorganisms.^[9] Some antibiotics are synthetically derived

compound, synthesized in the laboratories from different strains of microorganisms and these strain on continuous exposure to antimicrobials become mutant strain.

Antimicrobial resistance develops when the bacteria adapt itself and develops certain resistant mechanism to cope with the antimicrobial action. If a bacterium become resistant then it is very difficult to treat the infection and it is hard to treat that infection and illness and can transmitted from person to community and in some cases, it turns very lethal.^[10] The use of antimicrobials in uncontrollable manner are the major cause of resistance against the pathogens. There are many foods which interact with the antimicrobial drugs such as milk, cheese foods containing calcium, magnesium and casein and these foods interferes with the bioavailability of the antibiotics and hinder their absorption. From 1960s to 1980s pharmaceutical industries developed so many antibiotics, against the microbial resistance mechanism but due the irrationally use of antimicrobials the situation is becoming worsen.^[11] This antimicrobial resistance is an schematic health problem that is increasing day by day in an exponential rate and it is exempted that due to antimicrobial resistance the approximately 15 million death crossed by 2050.^[12] The rapid use of antibiotics, without any proper diagnosis and management proves that there should be an strict action for this. In most of the hospitals in western countries the antimicrobial testing is performed by using culture techniques.

The susceptible microorganism is cultured in the media and nutrient media is supplied externally after this the resistant gene can be identified having resistant factors as for example the presence of *mecA* gene for methicillin resistant staphylococcus aureus, but the presence of genetic factor is essential for having the antimicrobial resistance, phenotypic adaption so called phenotypic susceptibility and this was found in carbapenem resistant bacteria and these bacteria's do not carry the carbapenemase genes but they develops reduced permeability, porin loss and also by the combination of upregulation of efflux pumps.^[13] This phenotypic response in the beta lactam class of antibiotic influences the 70% of the world population and their mode of action is through the inhibition of the transpeptidase activity of the penicillin binding protein and also preventing the peptidoglycan synthesis which is present in the cell wall.^[14] According to the report of international union committee of AMRs more than the 70% of world population is facing the problem related to the resistant action caused by the beta lactam antibiotics, and there is an emergence of the many pneumoniae related species that are resistant to the carbapenem antibiotics for example klebsiella pneumonia also the

carbapenem resistant Enterobacteriaceae CRE, and these resistant strains are the crucial cause of hospital mortality in the patient of upper respiratory disorder and septicemia.^[15] The antimicrobial resistance leads to the natural selection for the remaining microbes after the removal of drug sensitive bacteria's and these selected microbial genes through gene transfer mechanism imparts the resistance phenomena.^[16] In aminoglycosides class of antibiotic, the mode of resistance by bacteria is acquired through the modification of enzymes, through efflux ribosomal mutation and by the methylation of 16s ribosomal unit of RNA.

The quinolones class of antibiotics like ciprofloxacin, ofloxacin, norfloxacin undergoes their mode of action by the inhibition of DNA replication through efflux mechanism and mutation also played important role as mechanism. Altered cell wall synthesis as a mechanism takes place in glycopeptides like vancomycin, mainly efflux mechanism is present in the tetracyclines and enzymatic cleavage and efflux modification takes place in streptogramins which includes virginiamycin, Quinupristin, and Dalfopristin.^[17] Oxazolidinones like linezolid initiate the mode of action through the mutation in the 23s r RNA genes and also by the gene mutation phenomena. The antimicrobial resistant mechanism leads to the development of superbugs and the infections related to these superbugs are not treatable with that particular antibiotics. Further the development of new antibiotics is not an easy task as the situation is alarming day by day and also the antimicrobial resistance phenomena found in the animals, plants water, soil, air as these factors serves to transfer the resistant mechanism. The improper use of antibiotics, use of hazardous chemicals in agriculture not having proper sanitation, poor hygiene condition all these together quantify in the spreading of antimicrobial resistance and threatens the world and this requires an efficient monitoring system to handle this global threat.

According to the global report 2018 approximately three million people becoming resistant to particular class of antibiotics, and scientist, health departments are trying to reduce the resistant infections, the serious and alarming threats are from carbapenem- resistant Acinetobacter, carbapenem resistant Enterobacteriaceae, ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae, vancomycin- resistant enterococci (VRE), MRSA. Current reports on the antimicrobial resistance states that now microorganisms are acquiring resistant against the azoles, class of antibiotics as in Azole- resistant *Aspergillus fumigatus*. Carbapenem – resistant Enterobacteriaceae (CRE) is nearly resistant to all the antibiotics through enzyme modification, called as nightmare bacteria, causes serious internal infections, Clostridioides

difficile causes inflammation of colon and serious diarrhea. Extended- spectrum beta lactamase produces severe health complication in the community of healthy people. They masked the potential of antibiotics like penicillin, and cephalosporins.^[18] Several initiatives have been taken all over the world to tackle this global health issue, in India there are many NGOs working for the proper surveillance of the antibiotic delivery and its consumption, these NGOs are completely working under the guiding principles of WHO, and the main aim to impart knowledge about the ill effect of using antimicrobial blindly.

Antimicrobials

Antimicrobials are the agents which are used against the microbes and pathogens such as bacteria, viruses, fungi, antimicrobials can either kill them or retards their growth. Antimicrobials are the broad class they can be categorized into antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, antiprotozoal, anti sporulant.

Categorization of antimicrobials antimicrobials can be categorized on the basis of several fields like – on the basis of mode of action such as- cell wall synthesis inhibitors- (Beta lactam antibiotics inhibits the transpeptidase, vancomycin inhibits trans glycosylase, Fosfomycin inhibits enol pyruvate transferase, cycloserine inhibits alanine racemase and ligase, bacitracin inhibits bactoprenol dephosphorylation).

Protein synthesis inhibitors-(aminoglycosides, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, macrolides), through disruption of cell membrane (polypeptide antibiotics like polymyxin b, colistin tyrothricin, amphotericin b, nystatin, azoles like ketoconazole fluconazole) nucleic acid inhibitors-(DNA gyrase inhibitors or topoisomerase inhibitors like quinolones, fluoroquinolones, novobiocin RNA polymerase inhibitors- rifampicin, antimicrobial destroying DNA-nitrofurantoin, metronidazole) antimicrobials that are analogues of nucleosides or nucleotides- idoxuridine, acyclovir, NRTIs ,metabolism inhibitors-(sulphonamides, dapson, para amino salicylic acid inhibits folic acid synthesis, trimethoprim, pyrimethamine, proguanil and methotrexate inhibits dihydrofolate reductase, ethambutol inhibits the synthesis of arabinogalactan).^[19]

Type of organism on which the antimicrobial is active (antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal and many others) their range of activity (broad or narrow spectrum), potency of activity (cidal or static), their post antibiotic effect.

The antimicrobials having bacteriostatic action are sulfonamides, dapson, trimethoprim, ethambutol, whereas bactericidal are polypeptides class like polymyxins, colistin, amphotericin-B, penicillin, cephalosporin cycloserine. The killing activity of antimicrobial is either concentration dependent or time dependent, those antimicrobial in which killing effect is concentration dependent like- fluoroquinolones, aminoglycosides have higher ratio of peak concentration as compared to the minimum inhibitory concentration. The antimicrobials whose killing effect is dependent on the internal time exposure to the antibiotics like- beta lactam antibiotics, macrolides.^[20] In determining the potential of antimicrobials post antibiotic effect is the important criteria, it is the inhibitory action of the anti-microbials when their concentration is below the minimum inhibitory concentration.

The antimicrobials having long post antibiotic effect are beta lactam class of antibiotics, glycopeptides, protein synthesis inhibitors, (tetracycline, ketolides clindamycin, linezolid), metabolism inhibitors (sulphonamides, trimethoprim), nucleic acid inhibitors (fluoroquinolones, rifampicin), daptomycin.^[21] Generally the long acting antimicrobials have post antibiotic effect greater than or equal to 1.5 hour, and mostly active against the gram positive bacteria, some are also having the post effect against gram negative bacteria like quinolones, aminoglycosides, and chloramphenicol.^[22] on the basis of therapeutic effect antimicrobials can be of high therapeutic index or low therapeutic index.

Antibiotics

These are the substance which is produced from different microorganisms, they can either kill or retard the growth and metabolism of microorganisms. Examples of certain antibiotics- Beta lactam antibiotics, glycopeptides, chloramphenicol, tetracycline, macrolides, lincosamides, ketolides etc. Resistance of microbes- microorganisms are said to be resistant to the antibiotics, when the given drug not produces the desired therapeutic action against the microbes as, they develop resistance against the antimicrobial drugs.

Types of drug resistance

On the basis of adaptability

1. Natural resistance
2. Acquired resistance

Natural resistance is of innate types that is present in the microorganisms, against the antimicrobial drugs.

Acquired resistance is adapted by the microorganisms by the mutation in their genetic makeup.

On the basis of mutation

1. Single step mutation
2. Multi step mutation

Drugs with single step mutation- streptomycin and rifampicin

Drugs with multi step mutation - tetracycline, erythromycin, chloramphenicol

The resistance action of microorganisms against the drug can be transferred from one microorganism to another, by following modes: -

Transfer of through transformation, transduction, conjugation

The question which come inside the mind that how the microorganisms become resistant to anti-microbials

There are several action mechanisms regarding this which is developed by the microorganism

- a. By hindering the target affinity as – penicillin binding protein
- b. By acquiring different metabolic pathway-sulphonamides
- c. Drug inactivation- Beta lactamase (penicillin, cephalosporins)
- d. Altering the permeability of drug (aminoglycosides, tetracycline)
- e. Through efflux pumps (tetracycline, fluoroquinolones)

Antibiotics are the great discoveries in the modern world but day by day it become very challenging.as the microbes, bacteria develop resistance.

The development of resistance is inherent properties or may be acquired by the bacteria. As in the present scenario in corona period the major challenge is due to the virus resistance, which threatens the world, and causes major human destruction.^[23]

Mainly the drug resistance is seen in tuberculosis so the drug regimen is very constrained. Several other factors also responsible for the anti-microbial resistance such as certain metals, chemicals, carbamates, phosphates etc. resistance gene present inside the microbes causes the degradation of the antibiotics. For example, penicillin resistant gene in the penicillinase bacteria also in methicillin resistant staphylococcus aureus.^[24] These bacteria degrade the

beta lactam ring and decreases the torsion strain present in the penicillin ring, as there is not any fixed time period at which the anti-microbial resistance develops, but on prolonging use of the particular antibiotic resistance to it generally occur.^[25] People have to be aware of the curb causing due to the bad and more ill effect of using antibiotics, and not to use all antibiotics in the initial stage of disease.

The antimicrobial resistance is somewhat the matter of adaptability and sustainability regarding that antibiotic or antimicrobial. As in case of sulpha meth oxazole, trimethoprim these are used against cholera in previously but in present scenario bacteria are prone to them and this is very much due to antimicrobial resistance.^[26] Methicillin is the most prominent antibiotic, having the resistant against the penicillin and this is done by altering the methyl group substitution in the side chain of Penam structure.

This is only single example regarding the method to cope up with the antimicrobial resistance, but many questions arise in the mind: - as what are the gene level changes in the microorganisms that causes the resistance?

Generally microbial resistance theory relies on two aspects

1. Pharmacological way of anti-microbial resistance
2. Chemical modification of anti-microbial resistance

Pharmacological basis of anti-microbial resistance- on the basis of pharmacology certain genes are present inside the microorganisms which initiate the resistance mechanism as, in many gram-negative bacteria there is presence of metallo beta lactamase enzyme that sufficiently hinder the antibiotics activity.^[27] These enzymes potentially suppress the multidrug therapy.

Not only the gram negative but these enzymes resist the carbapenem mode of action and also, they are responsible for the several for the hospital acquired infections.

The statical data about these resistant in India ranges from 10 to 70%, this huge difference indicate that the resistance is effective from small to Large population and also due to exhaustive use of antimicrobial. The trend of continuously and regularly use of antibiotic increases the resistance tendency.^[28] Other resistance case in MRSA, i.e. methicillin resistant staphylococcus aureus causes several skin infections in the communities. As per recent study in India out of 391 individuals more the 150 are found to be resistant and they are suffering

ng from nasal infection, dermatitis and intoxication in extreme cases.^[29] Vancomycin resistant staphylococcus aureus, VRSA has increases the activity spectrum of the MRSA, and it spread the infection from hospital to the community also it accelerates the rate of infection.

In case of clindamycin the prevalence, of soft tissue infection increases and it also induce septic shock and pneumonia. In India more than 15% cases arises due to clindamycin associated resistant, and now the cases are increasing in hospitals.^[30] The resistance against the HIV i.e. anti-retro viral drugs is very common cause that induces genetic mutation in the microorganism, metallo-beta lactamase induces resistant against the anti-viral drugs.^[31] Multi drug resistance produces by extended spectrum beta lactamase i.e. ESBL is very common in India. This can decrease the potential of many powerful antibiotics and act as defense mechanism. Fluroquinolones are mainly used in urinary tract infection and to somewhat in skin infection but due to the production of plasmid mediated some proteins like qnr protein increases the resistant mechanism and decreases the therapeutic efficiency of fluroquinolones.^[32]

Nalidixic acid which was discovered in past 40 years ago, was a potent type but as the resistant first developed in USA its concomitant used has been decreased and new formulation for nalidixic being developed but in recent year certain pseudomonas species like aeruginosa and other gram negative bacteria.^[33]

In E. coli species there are some regions where the binding of quinolones takes place, these regions impart instability and causes degradation of the quinolone therapeutic activity. Many constitutive enzymes which are present inside the microbes having housekeeping function causes the efflux of the antibiotic and initiating the efflux pump. This pump also increases the mutation rate of the enzymes against the microorganisms, increases the efflux and decreases the influx of the antibiotics.^[34] The sulphonamides resistance is also a plasmid mediated, and hinder the potential activity of gram-negative bacteria, as it is mainly due to mutation in genes which is responsible for the synthesis of dihydropteroate synthesis, and causes antibiotic in activation.^[35] As due to the development of efflux pump multiple drug resistance has been developed in microorganism and it is the main mechanism to develop resistance. With the development of these pumps certain microbes develops co-resistance along with others antibiotic.^[36]

The metabolic product and the process involved imparts resistant mechanism to the microorganisms for example-hydrolysis, phosphorylation, acetylation, nucleotidylation, monooxygenation, glycosylation, efflux, ADP ribosylation alteration in the target lysis in carbon and oxygen.^[37] All these resistant mechanism via metabolic products are specific to certain antibiotic class. Acetylation is against mode of resistance chloramphenicol and ciprofloxacin.

Peptidoglycan biosynthesis is mode of resistance against the mechanism of Vancomycin and Teicoplanin, Hydrolysis along with target alteration generally takes place against Beta lactam class, certain microorganisms develops resistance by the lysis of carbon oxygen bond against streptogramins like synergids, ADP- ribosylation is adapted against the rifamycin, efflux mechanism also present against the sulphonamides like sulphamthoxazole.^[38] Aminoglycosides and tetracycline spectrum activity lost due to the decrease in drug permeability by pneumococci.

Next question arises that how one can generally decide and find out the genes or the factors involved in developing the antimicrobial resistance, resistance imparting factors: - as we can classify antimicrobial as antibiotics, antifungal, disinfectant, surfactants, also some chemicals and solvents like nonpolar i.e. cyclohexane, toluene, chloroxylenol etc.^[39] All these factors come under the environmental effect which additionally enhances the resistance activity and also the selectivity of antimicrobials. These factors also act as a driving forces for antimicrobial resistance.^[40] Some gene imparts resistance to another gene and thus induces the resistance so called co-resistance.

FACTORS IMPARTING ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE

Tremendous use of antibiotics

As per research that was done in 2014 in U.K the consumption of antibiotics was 30.2DDD per 1500 people and this data is increasing at a constant rate since 2014, according to the WHO report India was the largest consumer of antibiotics, in 2011 and it was followed by china, Australia, New Zealand these countries spend 75 to 85 unit per capita, unit means the doses in the form of tablets and capsules or in form of pills.^[41]

As people are getting aware of the side effects of antibiotics the antibiotic usage has been decreased. Not having a proper knowledge about ill effect of using antibiotics increasing the day to day cases.^[42] Antimicrobial resistance cases are more prevalent in the south east Asian

countries as due to poor sanitation and malnutrition, lack of knowledge. These all increases the resistance condition and destroy the health system of the country.^[43]

Antimicrobial uses in combination

Excessive use of antimicrobials with combination produces serious adverse reaction and enhances the antimicrobial resistance in people, generally the antimicrobials which are bacteriostatic in action are more prevalent to resistance mechanism, also the combination effect of two or more antibiotics shows additive action, in case of bactericidal the combination therapy is used only if the microorganism or bacteria is responding to both drugs.^[44]

Lack of control on using the antibiotics

As there is not any law regarding the exhaustive use of antibiotics, no policy or any national programme that has strictly imposed by the government on the irregular sale of these antibiotics, as they are the “soft weapon” which slowly but certainly hampers the individual health and ultimately to whole health system.^[45] For example, a study relates that vancomycin resistant was developed in about 18% of individual in India. As there is no proper monitoring authority in between the community that provide data and also guides regarding these resistances against the anti-microbials.^[46] High use of urinary antibiotics that is fluoroquinolones, nalidixic acid increase the resistance spectrum against the antimicrobial tools, these all also seen in the case of antitubercular drugs, so that the drug regimen of anti TB drugs are very specific and should be strictly followed, also there should be proper control on the dosage and regimen, if someone not follow the procedure of taking the anti TB drugs.^[47]

Not completing the adequate drug dose for treatment

This leads to the development of multidrug resistance as cited above that in case of tuberculosis, skipping any particular dose make the bacteria resistant to that drug and then different drug regimen has to introduce in the treatment of that particular disease.^[48] Antibiotics are tremendously use in the treatment of various diseases in animals and they also get acquired the resistant phenomena. In herds and flocks’ John’s disease is a very chronic one and in general there is no, such proper drug which is very effective, but antibiotics Monensin is very effective which is a polyether derivative.^[49] As a report in 2015 (veterinary official department) more than 18% of the cattle are in resistant to this antibiotic.

Most of the European countries banned the use of antibiotics and this tendency is declining in north America and other countries. The use of antibiotics in food production by many food suppliers like McDonalds are in phase to reduce the use of antibiotics mostly in poultry cases, as on consuming these foods people becomes resistant to those antibiotics which was used during food processing.^[50]

Over the counter selling of antibiotic

In India and other Asian countries, the cases, of antimicrobial resistance increases day by day and this is due to its OTC sale, and there are not any standard operating guidelines that enforces against the over the counter sailing of antibiotics but now the several government bodies, public health bodies are monitoring the hazards of antimicrobial resistance in hospitals and in other public health departments. When the microbes become resistant to particular antibiotics or multiple antibiotics the therapeutic level increases against the resistant strain of microbes.

Low cost of antibiotics

As low cost of some antibiotic enhances their sale in irregular and uncontrolled manner and imparting resistance, it is very easy for any person to take antibiotics without the permission of health professionals and the resistance is gradually developed inside the body.^[51] This is more common with the excessive use of fluroquinolones and aminoglycosides; they also result in the uncertainties in bioavailability and compatibility with the physiological conditions of individuals.^[52] Among the mentioned antibiotics oxytetracycline, doxycycline, and sulfadiazine are mostly used, followed by lincomycin, flumequine and tylosin for veterinary purposes. Due to their extensive use and easy reach to the community the resistances are very common, in human as well as in animals. According to us survey report about 18% of the lactating cows are on treatment with the antimicrobials and more common one is penicillin and other one is cephalosporins.

Transfer of resistance

The transfer of antimicrobial resistance, through resistance genes takes place through contamination in water, biocides and some heavy metals, sewage water all these factors are under the environmental control and externally influence the resistance mechanism.^[53] As large number of antibiotics are consumed by the people and these antibiotics after biotransformation get excreted from the body in the form of feces and urine, as these are in their biologically active form and transfer these resistances as a cycle.^[54] All these create an

antimicrobial resistance pathway, that is cyclic involving the physical, chemical and biological means.

Antimicrobial resistance present in bacteria

In *E. coli* there occurs a resistant mechanism against the fluoroquinolones, used for the urinary tract infections, and in many European countries this treatment is ineffective in more than half of patients.^[55] Like this bacterium, *Klebsiella* which is also an Enterobacteriaceae, responsible for the life-threatening infections, and these species are resistant to the carbapenem class of antibiotics.^[56] The bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* is very common, causes severe infections and more than half of world population are with methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), mortality rate is higher in patients due to this resistance as compared to the side reactions of drugs.^[57] There's an widespread resistance development in case of *N. gonorrhoea* and it is resistance to penicillin, tetracyclines, macrolides, and fluoroquinolones, in most countries ceftriaxone is used in the injectable form against this infection.

Third generation cephalosporins are somewhat effective in MRSA but in middle east countries its effectiveness decreases.^[58] There are many factors by which bacteria become antimicrobial resistance, and one of them is through the selective pressure, and it is a natural phenomena in which all bacteria are not responsive and susceptible to the particular antibiotic but some are that can multiply in presence of that antibiotic and a whole population of bacteria becomes resistant, selection pressure being natural cannot be stopped but the rate by which it increases can be decreased by not taking antibiotics in an uncontrollable manner, over use of antibiotics should be stopped to decrease the selection pressure.^[59] Overuse of antibiotics only kills the pathogens but also the good bacteria that protect the body from several infections, due course of time some strain develops resistance and these strains allowed to grow and these bacteria may transfer their gene resistance mechanism against the antibiotics to other bacteria, and thus the condition becomes more problematic. The genetic resistance that takes place in the bacteria gradually is the result of gene mutation, and the resistant infections proves as a major setback to the health care system.^[60]

The infections which are most common result of antimicrobial resistance includes, urinary tract infection, septicemia, sexually transmitted diseases, most commonly gonorrhoea skin infection, tuberculosis, internal wound, pneumonia, and many more Generally, very young or the elderly patient are at the verge of these resistant infections, patient that undergone

surgeries, dialysis or undergoing chemotherapy, organ transplantation as their immune system is compromised (immune- comprised).^[61] Antimicrobial resistance genes and various mobile elements are crucial for initiating resistance.

Tests to identify the antimicrobial resistant bacteria

There are several laboratory tests that are used to identify the resistant bacteria with their cultured techniques, these are-

1. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing
2. Molecular testing
3. Genome sequencing of bacterial DNA
4. Carbapenemase production test
5. Colonization screening
6. Carrier identification
7. Dilution method
8. Disk- diffusion method
9. E-test
10. Automated method
11. Genotypic methods (PCR, DNA hybridization method)
12. Beta lactamase detection test

The most common anti-microbial resistance test is antimicrobial susceptibility test (AST) this test commonly known as sensitivity testing. In AST the sample is taken from the infectious cell and it is cultured in media to identify the bacteria, AST determine the rate of effectiveness of the particular antimicrobial against the bacteria or other microorganism.^[62]

Molecular testing involves the process in which the gene imparts resistance, is identified and then that specific gene is isolated diagnosed and sequencing of total bacterial genome is performed.^[63]

Carbapenemase production test is used to found that, the bacteria are producing carbapenemase enzyme that nullify the effect of carbapenem antibiotic.

The dilution method involves both microdilution and macro dilution in the broth volumes, its main aim is to identify and isolate the concentration of antimicrobials in the medium. In microdilution the volume will be about 0.05 to 0.1ml whereas in case of macro dilution

volume will be 1.0ml.^[64] In this test the minimum inhibitory concentration for the antibiotic will be determined.

Antimicrobial resistance in mycobacterium tuberculosis

The strains of mycobacterium tuberculosis prove a global threat and as epidemic in the population of world, and the new cases are multi drug resistant TB(MDR-TB). The MDR-TB are mainly resistant to the rifampicin known as rifampicin resistant TB(RR-TB). According to the WHO report 2018, about half of the world population will become resistant to the rifampicin (RR-TB).^[65-70] The side effect related to the multidrug resistant cases are gastrointestinal disturbances, peripheral neuropathy, hypothyroidism, seizures, ototoxicity, and nephrotoxicity. Tuberculosis is a curable if the drug regimen is properly followed by the diseased person and health care departments, if the patient is resistant to first line of drugs that is rifampicin and isoniazid than it is multidrug resistant TB Whereas in case of XDR TB the patient is resistance to fluoroquinolones and one of the second line drugs like amikacin, or kanamycin along with the rifampicin and isoniazid.^[71-75] The extensively drug resistant form of tuberculosis is more prevalent in the middle east countries and it is increasing as an alarming rate.

Antimicrobial resistance in viruses

Antiviral drug resistance is more prevalent in the immune compromised patients, over use of antiviral therapy may increase the adaptability potential of the microorganism also enhances the selection pressure, and a greater number of viruses resistant to the drug, these antiviral drugs influences the selective pressure, which kills the susceptible microbes and allows the antibiotic resistant microbes to survive and multiply.^[76-80] Antiviral agents inhibit the replication of virus at any of the stages, after the fusion of virus into the host cell, like - viral fusion then penetration, uncoating, early protein synthesis, nucleic acid synthesis, late protein synthesis, packaging and at last the release of virus.

All these successive steps are inhibited by specific anti-viral drugs. Almost all the antiviral drugs are becoming ineffective against the viruses, due to the resistance mechanism of viruses.^[81-85] According to the WHO report 2019, almost 20% population of Asia and Latin America are resistant to non- nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NNRTIs). In sub-Saharan Africa the people are resistant to the first line regimen against HIV.^[86-90]

Another mean of antibiotic resistance in bacteria is through target protection which involves the interaction of the resistance gene which is actually protein with the drug and this is very selective, and highly specific phenomena, it brings a conformational change in the target site and then it is either dissociate from the complex or remains there with the antibiotic.^[91-93] For example, tetracycline class of antibiotics exhibits this target protection and tetracycline was the first antibiotic in which target protection was scientifically observed. Tetracycline acts by inhibiting the translation mechanism by inhibiting with the 30 s ribosomal unit, the genes which codes for the tetracycline ribosomal protection proteins are specific in terms of gram positive and gram-negative strains of bacteria.^[94-97]

Clinically this resistant mechanism has the ability as active efflux of the antibiotic and prolongs the target protection in tetracycline. The resistance as mediated by the tetracycline class of antibiotic has the ability to overcome the first generation of tetracycline, the class of antimicrobials that targets the 50s ribosomal subunit are lincosamides, azolidines and ketolides derivatives. The defense strategies access by the microorganisms may be due to internal cause or by external, environmental effect, they either change the antibiotic target, get rid of the antibiotic effect, degrades the antibiotic effect causing the structural deformation, develops new process against the inhibitory action of antibiotics.^[98-101]

Antimicrobial resistance in fungi

Resistance to antibiotic, in case of fungi, mostly occurs through the genetic recombination, there is changes in genomes, DNA sequences that codes for the proteins and RNAs. The cells transfer these resistances to other cell and become virulent to the organisms.^[102-105] The presence of cytochrome genes in the pathogenic fungus is mainly responsible for the detoxification process, and there is widespread resistance present against amphotericin B, fluconazole, voriconazoles. Most of the fungal resistant are hospital borne and they are highly contagious, latest report in the fungal resistance case is from capsosfungin, that was very active against the fungal spores. As per WHO report 2018, 20% population of middle east gained the resistance against *Candida auris*, generally the polyene antibiotics has very low bioavailability for example nystatin, the spores of fungal mycelium are much resistant to the nystatin forming the ring like structure on skin surface.^[106-111] Antifungal resistance proves itself as a major challenge to the health department and practitioner, azoles derivatives like-ketoconazole, fluconazole, itraconazole are now days used only superficially, due to the resistance developed in fungi.^[112-116]

According to us health department one fourth of its population are resist to azole derivatives, somehow voriconazole is effective one. *Aspergillus fumigatus* causes chronic pulmonary disease and responsible for high death rate in middle east countries, this pathogen generally affects the immunodeficient people.^[117-121] Generally, the fungi of Ascomycota class are very much resistant to the azole derivatives, and also having adverse effect such as blurred vision, photophobia and actinic keratosis.

Mechanisms of mobile antibiotic resistance

Pathogenic bacteria can acquire antibiotic resistance (ABR) genes through two main mechanisms of horizontal gene transfer (HGT): conjugation and transduction. Compensatory mutations alleviate the fitness costs imposed by ABR genes, contributing to their stabilization. CRISPR-Cas-based systems may selectively destroy DNA carrying mobile ABR genes.

Fig. 1: Mechanisms of mobile antibiotic resistance.

C RISPR-Cas- clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats

ABR gene – antibiotic resistance gene, present in plasmids

HGT- Horizontal gene transfer, horizontal gene transfer also known as lateral gene transference and it involves the transfer of gene from unicellular or multicellular organism.

Conjugation, transduction, transformation are the means through which the resistance can be transferred from one microorganism to another.

Plasmid- self-replicating and autonomous body.

CONCLUSION

Antimicrobial resistance in the microbes and other pathogens, creating serious health issue in the world communities, through these resistance people are immune to particular antimicrobials, and side effect are also very prominent. Statical data are increasing day by

day, for this a proper management system should be present and the communities should be well informed regarding the use of antimicrobials and its side reaction and it should be the duty of every health individual to follow the rule in prescribing the antimicrobials, and their delivery to the patient.

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